

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

Prado, N. B. do; Moraes, G. H. S. M. de; Synodinos, C. (2025). Environmental concern and attitude: the mediating role of environmental knowledge. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(6), e2024-0341. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250604>

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Reviewers:

The first reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Karla Menezes , Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal, Escola Superior de Ciências Empresariais, Setubal, Portugal
Ihwan Ghazali , Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka, Faculty of Industrial and Manufacturing Technology and Engineering, Melaka, Malaysia

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Ihwan Ghazali

Date review returned: 13-Jul-2024

Recommendation: Major Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

You stated ” Based on these arguments, this study aims to analyze the antecedents of environmental attitudes among green beauty product consumers in a developing country. More specifically, it aims to investigate the influence of environmental concern and environmental knowledge on environmental attitude, as well as the mediation role of environmental knowledge in the relationship between environmental concern and environmental attitude.

These statements do not reflect the research gaps. Please highlight your research gap in this section paragraph.

“Cosmetic users play a significant role in contributing to or reducing pollution through their choice and use of products (Munerah et al., 2021). Hence, new trends have been created in the green cosmetics field, like food supplements to use for skin, hair, and nails, additionally to nutricosmetics (Dini & Laneri, 2021).

Your paragraph is too short as a paragraph, please make longer paragraph by combining short short paragraph, do it for all paragrarph

Avoid “We” in your manuscript, seems too many “we” in your writing

Hypothesis for H8 argumentation is too weak, please add your argument.

Initially, we analysed the sample profile. 50.8% were female, while 48.6% were male and 0.6% selfdeclared as non-binary or preferred not to declare. Age varied between 18 and 65 years old, with a mean of 36 years old. 87.4% live in the urban area, more specifically in the Gauteng province (41.6%). Regarding the beauty product usage behaviour, the most frequent are respectively: toiletries, skincare products, haircare products, fragrances, and colour (make-up)

This profile of respondents needs to be set in a Table.

Your argumentation in discussion seems to weak, you need to make stronger argumentation with supporting references.

The Figure model need to be clearer

Highlight the contribution of your study for knowledge and practice more detail.

Reviewer 2 Report

The reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

The reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Reviewer 2 Report

Reviewer: Karla Menezes

Date review returned: 13-Jul-2024

Recommendation: Major Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

Dear authors, the article presents a current and relevant topic, and I congratulate you on your choice. However, some points for improvement are suggested, namely the basis for the unconfirmed hypotheses, especially those related to consumer awareness and trust in green products. It is also recommended that greater exploration of the cultural and socioeconomic particularities of South Africa be carried out to make the results more generalizable and applicable in management practice. Furthermore, the inclusion of additional procedures in the validation of the scales would significantly increase the credibility and academic impact of the research. The attached document contains the comment.

Paper Objectives:

The objectives are relevant and aligned with the growing importance of sustainability and green consumer behavior in the management and marketing literature, given the growing interest in environmental issues and the importance of sustainability in consumption. Although the objectives are clearly presented and aligned with the general proposal, a significant limitation regarding originality is observed. The study could have better highlighted the differential of investigating this phenomenon in a developing country, specifically in South Africa, given that current literature already intensively addresses the relationship between environmental concerns, knowledge and attitudes.

Literature Review:

The literature review provides adequate coverage of the core concepts related to sustainable consumption and environmental attitudes. However, the analysis is predominantly descriptive, without a deeper critique of the contradictions or limitations of the studies cited. The inclusion of recent references is a strength, but the absence of fundamental classical works weakens the theoretical basis. A more critical and less descriptive discussion of the theoretical models adopted would have provided a more solid basis for the research. The authors refer to previous studies that support the relationship between these variables, using recent sources that contribute to the theoretical foundation. However, there could be an expansion in the discussion of literature that explores contrasts in different developing countries, providing a more comprehensive view of consumer behavior in different contexts.

Hypotheses:

The article proposes eight hypotheses logically derived from the literature review and the theoretical framework presented. However, some hypotheses could have been initially explained in greater detail, such as H4 and H8, which would have strengthened the argument. Two other hypotheses about awareness and trust in green products were not empirically confirmed (H1: Awareness of green beauty products positively influences environmental concern and H2: Trust in green beauty products positively influences environmental concern), which may indicate a conceptual weakness in the choice of these variables or failures in the adaptation of the scales and raise questions about the robustness of the concept and the suitability of the scales used in the study, suggesting that they may not have been appropriate for the specific context of green beauty products. In this context, the hypotheses require further theoretical revision or a more solid justification for their inclusion, given that their results contradict robust findings previously reported in the literature. Furthermore, the study does not sufficiently delve into the reasons why the constructs “awareness” and “trust” were not significant. A detailed and more critical explanation of why these variables failed to influence the construct of environmental concern would contribute significantly to theoretical robustness and to the advancement of knowledge on the subject.

From a methodological point of view, the use of PLS-SEM and the sample size are sufficient to validate the hypotheses. However, considering the complexity of the variables analyzed, a more rigorous validation of the scales adopted would be desirable, including additional exploratory analyses or a prior assessment of validity. Such a procedure would ensure greater robustness in the results, especially in the variables that did not present significance.

Theoretical Framework:

Although the framework presented is logical and detailed, there is room for improvement. The current model, although detailed, does not adequately consider contextual factors that may influence the relationships studied specifically in South Africa. Cultural, economic and social factors should have been discussed and included as potential moderators or control variables, which would have significantly enriched the model, contributing to greater practical and theoretical relevance of the findings.

Scale Validation:

Although the article uses scales adapted from previous validated studies, the process of adaptation and validation in the specific context of the research is not sufficiently detailed. The direct use of existing scales may be a weak point, since the original scales were developed in cultural, social or economic contexts different from the one studied (South Africa), which may result in interpretation distortions or biased responses from consumers, reducing the validity of the constructs in the specific context of the research. A detailed pre-test, accompanied by a more in-depth initial exploratory analysis, could verify whether the adapted scales maintain semantic and structural validity in the target population. The study presented does not clearly state whether such procedures were carried out with sufficient rigor before the final application of the research. Despite the confirmation of convergent and discriminant validity in the study, a prior exploratory analysis with complementary techniques (e.g. exploratory factor analysis – EFA) would be recommended, which would more robustly confirm the adequacy of the scales adopted before the use of PLS-SEM.

Sample:

Although the sample is numerically robust (500 respondents), the study does not satisfactorily discuss the representativeness of this sample for the context of South African consumers. Although statistically adequate, social, economic and cultural representativeness was not sufficiently demonstrated, limiting the generalizability of the findings.

Results:

The results presented are well described, with clarity and internal coherence. However, the findings that refute the hypotheses related to awareness and trust raise doubts about the adequacy of the measures used or about consumers' conceptual understanding of these constructs in the context studied. Therefore, further qualitative exploration of these unexpected results is recommended in future research, to better understand the reasons underlying these deviations.